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A Study on Work Life Balance and Job Satisfaction among Women Teachers- With Special Reference to Tirunelveli District

A. Benazir and Dr. S. Archana Bai

Abstract--- In the present scenario, work life balance for women employees is highly desirable and if there is no job satisfaction and consistency in life, it can create a dilemma for working women. Work life balance requires attaining equilibrium between professional work and personal life, so that it reduces friction between official and domestic life. The ultimate performance of any organization depends on the performance of its employees, which in turn depends on numerous factors. These factors can be related to job satisfaction or family or both. The objective of this research is to study the working environment and women's perception about the work life balance and job satisfaction, who are working in schools. Apart from it, another significant objective is to study effects of work life balance on job satisfaction and initiatives taken by the organizations for effective work life balance and its relation with the job satisfaction. Finding suggests that WLB can be achieved by the factors responsible for job satisfaction such as: supportive colleagues, supportive working conditions, mentally challenging work, equitable rewards and employee oriented policies etc.

Keywords: Family; Employee's satisfaction; Job; Performance; Productivity and Rewards etc.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE term "work life balance" was coined in 1986, although its usage in everyday language was pattern less for a number of years. Interestingly, work life programs existed as early as the 1930s. Before World War II, the W.K. Kellogg Company created four six-hour shifts to replace the traditional three daily eight-hour shifts, and the new shifts resulted in increased employee morale and efficiency. Life is a balancing act, and it is safe to say that almost everyone is seeking work/life balance. But what exactly is work life balance? We have all heard the term, and many of us complain that we don't have enough of it in our lives. Among women, the

frustrating search for work life balance is a frequent topic of conversation, usually translated into not enough time and/or support to do, to handle, to manage their work commitments or personal responsibilities.

In India the concern over work-life balance is gradually becoming a common talk especially for women employees. Work life balance is a state of equilibrium in which the demand of both professional and personal life is equal. Each role having different set of demands and when such role demands overlap, multiple problems are faced. In reality life and work over-lap and interact. In designing the work life policies, employer should think that the commitment of employees can make the difference between those companies which compete at the marketplace and those which cannot. A balanced life for women is one where they spread their energy and effort between key areas of importance. This study investigates the factors responsible for work life balance and job satisfaction level amongst the women teachers. Employees are greatest resource of an organization. Attracting and retaining the right people is critical to the success of an organization. When it comes to human environment, it focuses on human aspects that influence an employee's performance and job satisfaction. Job satisfaction has been defined as the degree to which employees have a positive & effective orientation towards employment by the organization. Work determines a person's worth and place in society and it influences one's psychological identity and sense of well being.

The term "work" is being used to paid work or employment. Work establishes one in the community of human kind. It links a person to others, advances the goals of culture, and gives purpose to one's existence. Work is a purposeful human activity which is directed toward the satisfaction of human needs and desires. It is obvious that work needs to be satisfying the job for a mutual beneficial relationship between employee and employer. Job satisfaction creates innovative ideas among the employees. Individuals may become more loyal towards the organization. Employees will be more satisfied if they get what they expected with efficient work life balance.

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II. IMPORTANCE OF WORK LIFE BALANCE AND JOB SATISFACTION

The working sphere of Women in India is changing at incredible pace due to progressive reduction in trade barriers, modern innovation in technologies, globally interconnected market place, cut throat competition and business rivalry and changing family and population patterns.

These factors bring out tense anxiety into the life of the women and then it is magnified many times if both the husband-wife work and they have children of growing age and old age parents.

This constant worry can cause disorder on the psychological comfort of the women due to a feeling of diminished control over one's life and a hopeless perception that there is never enough time to have a sensible stability and balance in life. Apart from it there are a variety of factors that make women employee feel positive or negative about their job. Moreover, some employees may be satisfied with a few aspects of their work but dissatisfied with all other aspects. Factors that lead to hold positive or negative perceptions of their job have their own impact on work life balance. This mental stress for women can lead to physical stress and cause ill health, headache, gastritis, body ache, de-motivation, low morale etc., lead to long term cardiac problems, high blood pressure, diabetes or other psychiatric problems and low job performance etc. All these problems generate Work life conflict and job dissatisfaction especially for women employees, which results in:

- Increased Absenteeism
- Increased Employee Turnover
- Reduced Productivity
- Reduced Job Satisfaction
- Increased Managerial Stress
- Damage of Family and Social relationship

A positive and healthy employee oriented culture translates into increased job satisfaction and productivity while work life imbalance causes relationship degradation and job dissatisfaction for women employees.

III. EFFECTS OF WORK LIFE BALANCE AND JOB SATISFACTION

Without achieving work life balance job satisfaction cannot be attained. Work life conflict and job dissatisfaction will leads to the following situations

- Employees Punctuality, Teamwork, Customer service, work supervision responsibility, group behaviour, peer interaction and leadership initiative by workers are reduced.
- Creativity, new job-expertise learning and innovation of worker are grossly damaged due to

lowering of work related enthusiasm among employees.

- Employees having problem balancing work roles and family roles, set bad standard in the company work setting and often upset the friendly work ambience.
- Employees problems get reflected negatively on company's turnover, operating profit and balance sheet.
- Substantial increase in the cases of workers being absent on the job and in extreme cases leaving the job.

IV. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Review of related literature is an important step in undertaking research. It helps in clarifying and defining the problem, stating objectives, formulating hypotheses, selecting appropriate design and methodology of research as well as interpreting the results in the light of the research work already undertaken

Elizabeth A. Smith (2008) in his article about importance of work-life balance said that the flexible working helps to keep the staff motivated. The policy has also enhanced the company's reputation with both clients and employees.

Baral (2010) in a study of 485 employees working in varied organizations in India found that working men and women in India experience more work family enrichment than the work family conflict. It was also found that there were no gender differences in the employee perception of work family enrichment.

K. Santhana Lakshmi, T. Ramachandran, and David Boohene(2012) explained in their study that Majority of women are working through-out week and 53% are struggling to achieve work-life balance. Women reported that their life has become a juggling act as they have to shoulder multiple responsibilities at work and home.

Muhammad Sajjad et. al,(2013). In his study states that Employees can't enjoy their job if they are working with tactless and inflexible manager.

V. RESEARCH DESIGN

- The study is a descriptive survey study.
- Primary data is collected through self structured questionnaire
- Data are collected from 50 women teachers.

VI. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To study the working environment in schools for the point view of WLB & Job satisfaction.

- To study the perception about work life balance and job satisfaction among the working women teachers.
- To study the effects of work life balance on job satisfaction amongst the working women teachers.

DATA PRESENTATION, INTERPRETATION & ANALYSIS

7.1 How is the working environment in your organization?

S.NO	Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
1	Participative	21	42
2	Autonomy	15	30
3	Capricious	10	20
4	Red Tapism	04	8
Total		50	100

From the above table it is clear that in 40% and 30 % said that working environment in the organization is participative and autonomy respectively and 20 % and 30 % said that it is capricious and red tapism in that order. This reveals that majority of our respondents are participative in the working environment

7.2 Work allotted to you is according to your preference and skills?

S.No	Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
1	Strongly agree	15	30
2	Agree	20	40
3	Disagree	12	24
4	Strongly disagree	03	6
Total		50	100

From the above table it is obvious that 40 % were agree and 30% were strongly agree 50.55 % were agreeing. While 24% and 6 % were disagree and strongly disagree respectively. This shows that majority of our respondents agree that work is allotted according to their preference and skill.

7.3 Employees are satisfied with the policies of top management in your organization?

S.No	Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
1	Strongly agree	18	36
2	Agree	20	40
3	Disagree	10	20
4	Strongly disagree	02	4
Total		50	100

From the above table it is apparent that 36 % of respondents were strongly agree and 40% were agreeing and only 20 % and 4 % of respondents were disagree and strongly disagree about it respectively. This shows that majority of our respondents agree that they are satisfied with the policies of top management.

7.4 Physical working condition and working hours in your Organization is satisfactory?

S.No	Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
1	Strongly agree	20	40
2	Agree	18	20
3	Disagree	07	14
4	Strongly disagree	05	10
Total		50	100

From the above table it is understandable that 40% were strongly agree and 20% were agreeing. While 14 % and 10 % were disagree and strongly disagree respectively. This shows that physical working condition and working hours in their organization is much better.

7.5 Orientation programs for the employees are organized by the organization regularly?

S.No	Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
1	Strongly agree	16	32
2	Agree	18	36
3	Disagree	12	24
4	Strongly disagree	04	08
Total		50	100

From the above table it is understandable that 32 % were strongly agree and 36 % were agree While 24 % and 8% were disagree and strongly disagree respectively. This shows that majority of our respondents agree that their organization is conducting orientation programme regularly.

7.6 Employees have more pressure of work in the organization

S.No	Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
1	Strongly agree	25	50
2	Agree	12	24
3	Disagree	10	20
4	Strongly disagree	03	06
Total		50	100

From the above table it is understandable that 50 % were strongly agree and 24% were agree While 20 % and 6 % were disagree and strongly disagree respectively. This shows that majority of our respondents feel that they have more pressure of work in their organization.

7.7 Facilities provided by the organization to the employees are satisfactory?

S.No	Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
1	Strongly agree	10	20
2	Agree	20	40
3	Disagree	15	30
4	Strongly disagree	05	10
Total		50	100

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From the above table it is obvious that 20 % were strongly agree and 40 % were agree While 30 % and 10 % were disagree and strongly disagree respectively. This shows majority of our respondents agree that the facilities provided by the organization are satisfactory.

7.8 Do you think that if employees have good work-life balance then they will be more productive?

S.No	Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
1	Strongly agree	26	52
2	Agree	14	28
3	Disagree	08	16
4	Strongly disagree	02	04
Total		50	100

From the above table it is apparent that 52 % were strongly agree and 28 % were agree While 16 % and 4% were disagree and strongly disagree respectively. This shows that majority of our respondents strongly agree that having a good work life balance is a key to job satisfaction.

7.9 Your organization takes initiative to manage work and personal life of its employees?

S.No	Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
1	Strongly agree	10	20
2	Agree	14	28
3	Disagree	06	12
4	Strongly disagree	20	40
Total		50	100

From the above table it is clear that 20 % were strongly agree and 28 % were agree While 12 % and 40 % were disagree and strongly disagree respectively. This shows that majority of our respondents feels that the organization is not taking any initiative to manage their work and their personal life.

7.10 Your organization provides satisfactory compensation or non monetary rewards according to the Work?

S.No	Particulars	Respondents	Percentage
1	Strongly agree	14	28
2	Agree	16	32
3	Disagree	13	26
4	Strongly disagree	07	14
Total		50	100

From the above table it is understandable that 28 % were strongly agree and 32 % were agree While 26 % and 14.% were disagree and strongly disagree respectively. This shows that majority of the respondents agree that their organization provides satisfactory compensation according to the work.

VIII. FINDINGS

- Most of the women teachers found participative environment in their organization.
- WLB is an important determinant of intrinsic aspects of job satisfaction
- The working women are quite satisfied and view that somewhat they look education
- sector as a good place to work.
- Working hours are satisfactory in schools.
- Most of the teachers agree that work allotment is based on skills and qualification.
- High quality of work life balance will improve the job satisfaction and vice versa.

IX. CONCLUSIONS

Work life balance and job satisfaction is not a problem to be solved. These are ongoing issues to be managed. Work can dominate your life. Recognizing what is important and necessary and striving for what is valued will make a work-life balance feasible. Utilizing management skills will enable you to have a job satisfaction and balance between work and personal life. There are many causes for stress in the workplace and the possibility for eliminating all of them is impossible. The organization should consider Work-life balance and Job satisfaction of employees as an important input in designing appropriate policies for employees to address work - life balance and job satisfaction issues.

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